

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DOUANLA MAFODEM****FIRST NAME: LINDA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. What is Turabian Style? (EUCLID 2021, 40)
2. Abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 50)
3. Page Format (EUCLID 2021, 50)
4. Capitalization, Italics, and Quotes (EUCLID 2021, 47)

THE ARTS OF TURABIAN WRITING STYLE

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing an essay can be confusing as to which writing style to apply. Several writing styles exist, but in this write-up, we will focus on the Turabian writing style, also called the Chicago writing style. Before writing an essay, planning diligently and structuring ideas to provide a comprehensive and interesting write-up is advised. Referencing is a very important aspect of a written paper, as it helps show the reader that ideas defended in the paper are supported by previous research, and it also shows the level of integrity of the writer. For long documents, referencing becomes tedious, so Zotero, a modern app, helps with text citation, references, and bibliography. It could be downloaded freely and used with Word. When writing an essay, it is very important to diligently use appropriate language, i.e., American or British English. There are subtle differences between the two regarding spelling, grammar, syntax, punctuation, and general usage.

In this essay, we will be expatiating on the Turabian writing style, guidelines to follow, and expressions, and sharing some useful tips.

2) WHAT IS THE TURABIAN WRITING STYLE?

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. So, guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent (EUCLID 2021, 40).

A writing style includes presentation forms of abbreviations, page format, capitalization, italics/quotes, numbers & dates, quotations, footnotes, and bibliography.

a) Abbreviations

The Turabian style does not recommend using abbreviations in text but rather in figures, tables, parentheses, captions, and references. It is advised to refrain from beginning a sentence with abbreviations. Traditional forms of abbreviations and standard acronyms are accepted in the Turabian style.

‘Abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers... Writers and editors should monitor the number of different abbreviations used in a document; readers are trying to keep track of a large number of abbreviations, especially unfamiliar ones, will lose their way’ (EUCLID 2021, 44).

b) Page Format

The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) recommends:

- Margins: ‘The normal page dimensions are 8½ by 11 inches. Leave a margin of at least one inch on all four edges of the page. Some institutions require more, particularly on the left, where binding reduces the margin’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).
- Fonts: ‘The eminently readable Times Roman is perhaps the best choice... Twelve-point type (ten characters per inch) for text and ten-point (twelve characters per inch) for notes will meet the requirements of most institutions’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).
- Indents: ‘The standard indent is one-half inch. This applies to all indents: paragraphs, hanging indents in references, and block quotes’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).

- Paper: ‘Use only 8½ by 11-inch white paper. A 20-pound or 24-pound, high-brightness (80+) paper works best. Avoid or photocopy lighter papers (16 pounds or less) and textured papers such as an erasable bond’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).
- Justification: ‘Right margins should be justified (aligned) only if it can be done without leaving large gaps between words. When a computer automatically justifies lines, all hyphenation must be carefully checked and adjusted. While aligning text to the right margin makes for a neat page, it can be more difficult to read. Manuscripts submitted for publication use a ragged right margin for these reasons’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).
- Spacing: ‘The text should be double-spaced except for block quotations, notes [and references], captions, and long headings [that wrap to two lines], which should be single spaced with a blank space between items. The latter is sometimes called block paragraph spacing’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).
- Page numbers: ‘For each page beginning a major section of a paper (the first text page, bibliography, notes, appendix) are placed at the bottom center of the page three-quarters of an inch from the page edge. Page numbers on other pages go in the upper right corner, double spaced above the text’ (EUCLID 2021, 50).

c) Capitalization, Italics, and Quotes

i) *Capitalization*

Capitalization includes:

- Full capitalization is used only for major headings, in which every word is in capital letters.
- Heading capitalization is one in which every first and last word, noun, pronoun, adjective, and conjunction are in capitals.
- Sentence capitalization is one which has the first word of a title or a heading in capitals.

It is also common to capitalize titles of books, titles in foreign languages, geographic Names, and internet terminologies (e.g., website, email, etc.).

‘Italics and quotation marks are used in the text to highlight words, note and translate words in a language foreign to a reader, indicate irony (scare quotes), or mark words and letters that are referred to as words, not to the meaning they convey’ (EUCLID 2021, 47).

Quotations are placed in quotation marks, and include notes, citations, foreign language, added emphasis, and parenthetical citations.

i) *Italics and Quotes*

‘Italics and quotation marks are used in the text to highlight words, note and translate words in a language foreign to a reader, indicate irony (scare quotes), or mark words and letters that are referred to as words, not to the meaning they convey’ (EUCLID 2021, 47).

Quotations are placed in quotation marks and include notes, citations, foreign language, added emphasis, and parenthetical citations.

3) **CONCLUSION**

So many subtle details apply to following the Turabian writing style; a lot of diligence is needed to follow the subtle rules. This essay only explains some of it, but the EUCLID manual mentioned in the bibliography highlights the details in terms of language use and syntax, be it for American English or British English. The manual also highlights how to avoid plagiarism and grammatical errors.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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